

Tool 10

Ethical considerations

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 1 - Prepare), which helps you to make some prior ethical considerations related to your citizen science project. An ethical committee might provide more elaborate reflections and critical questions, but this will get you started.

This template can also be used as a starting point for an ‘information document’ to be added to informed consent forms as an annex. You can ask the citizen scientist to sign this as well.

This template is based on the [ACTION toolkit – Research ethics checklist](#), as well as the Research Ethics Protocol that was developed in [the SOCIO-BEE project](#).

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	CHECKBOX
Clear description about the goals of your citizen science research (project)	<i>Make sure your goals and principles are clearly stated, and that the document includes a clear description of the course of the project and which steps will be taken. This will help you reach a common vision with the participants, and will make your shared ambition feasible.</i>	•
Describe the level of engagement	<i>Make sure people know why they are targeted and know how they can contribute.</i> <i>Describe the level of engagement, e.g. to suggest new ideas, recommend improvements, participate in decision making, to make their voice heard, to allow for cooperation and dialogue, etc.</i>	•
Address motivations	<i>Clearly state what benefits participation in the project includes</i>	•

	<p>(e.g. social activities, learning opportunities, making an impact ...) and how the participants' contribution will be acknowledged in relevant publications and activities. Explain how this contribution might affect others in a positive way, either in the local community or in a broader sense (depending on the scope of the project).</p>	
Parental or third-party consent	<p>If you engage with minors or people who cannot give informed consent themselves, take special care to clearly explain, in plain and simple language, how they will be addressed, by whom, what is expected of them and how you intend to deal with any personal data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Refer to the privacy policy	<p>Make sure that next to the informed consent form and the accompanying information document, you also inform participants about your privacy policy. Data stewards or data protection officers at your institution can provide you with a template, or help you draft a clear statement/disclaimer people can agree with.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Inform involved stakeholders	<p>Do not only consider your 'target audience' who you want to take part in/contribute to the project, but also the people who are involved because of reasons other than participation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Explain rules and procedures	<p>For the information document, be sure to mention that 1) you will provide detailed instructions and/or trainings or workshops, and 2) participants are required to follow these instructions and only use the given tools for purposes related to project activities (if applicable). By letting people sign the information document as part of the informed consent, you can make sure they explicitly agree to this. You can explain why it is important to carefully follow these instructions: for their safety, but also, for</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •

	<i>example, to improve data quality and respect the rights and freedoms of fellow participants.</i>	
Provide contact details to talk about (research) ethics	<i>Make it clear how participants can reach you in an easy, private and comfortable way to inform you about these matters. Include this in your information document so participants know that you care about their (feelings of) safety and happiness and that there is a way to address problems and improve inclusion. If there are any risks involved, make sure participants are very well informed about the possible extent and the measures you foresee to limit these risks.</i>	•